

EVALUATION OF THE EFFECTIVENESS OF TRANSCRANIAL MAGNETIC STIMULATION IN DIFFERENT FREQUENCY MODES IN THE REGENERATION OF FACIAL NERVE FUNCTIONS IN PATIENTS WITH NEUROPATHY

Kuliyev Khusniddin Shamsievich

Of the Department of Neurology Bukhara State Medical Institute

Khodzhieva Dilbar Tajieвна

Head of the Department of Neurology, MD, Professor of the

Department of Neurology

Bukhara State Medical Institute

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Annotation. Facial nerve neuropathy is a common neurological condition characterized by unilateral weakening or complete lack of function of facial muscles due to damage to the VII cranial nerve. The incidence is approximately 20-30 cases per 100,000 population annually, and pathology can affect people of any age, significantly limiting their social activity and negatively affecting their psycho-emotional state. The idiopathic form (Bell's palsy) dominates the morbidity structure, accounting for approximately 70% of all diagnosed cases, while the remaining 30% are caused by traumatic injuries, infectious processes, neoplasms and metabolic disorders.

Key words: Transcranial magnetic stimulation, facial nerve neuropathy, Bell's palsy, neurorehabilitation, low-frequency stimulation, high-frequency stimulation, neuroplasticity, restoration of facial muscles, electroneuromyography, modulation of cortical excitability.

Introduction. Although the majority of patients experience spontaneous restoration of function within 3-6 months, a significant proportion (15-30%) suffer from long-term consequences in the form of persistent paresis of facial muscles, pathological synkinesias, contractures and hemifacial spasm. These residual phenomena not only disrupt the functional activity of a person, but also create serious psychosocial problems, including decreased self-esteem, anxiety-depressive disorders, and social isolation.

Modern therapeutic strategies for facial neuropathy include the use of glucocorticosteroids, antiviral drugs, vasoactive drugs, various physiotherapy techniques and exercises for facial muscles. In some cases, the possibility of surgical decompression of the nerve is being considered. Nevertheless, the effectiveness of these approaches remains controversial, which stimulates the search for innovative therapeutic techniques that can optimize and accelerate the regeneration of nervous tissue.

An analysis of potential predictors of the effectiveness of TMS showed that the best results with the use of high-frequency stimulation were observed in patients younger than 60 years old, with a disease duration of up to 14 days, in the absence of a complete block of facial nerve conduction according to initial electroneuromyography. Individual characteristics of the threshold of motor evoked potential also influenced the effectiveness of stimulation, which emphasizes the importance of a personalized approach to determining the parameters of TMS.

The safety of the studied TMS protocols is confirmed by the absence of serious adverse events. Transient side effects in the form of headache, discomfort in the stimulation area and dizziness were observed in 15% of patients, mainly with high-frequency stimulation, but did not require discontinuation of therapy.

Thus, the results of the study demonstrate the therapeutic potential of transcranial magnetic stimulation in accelerating and optimizing recovery processes in facial neuropathy. The differentiated use of protocols of different frequencies, taking into account the clinical characteristics of the disease and the individual characteristics of patients, makes it possible to maximize the effectiveness of neurorehabilitation. High-frequency TMS (10 Hz) may be recommended as an additional treatment for acute facial neuropathy, especially in patients with incomplete conduction block according to electroneuromyography.

Conclusions: Thus, a promising area of further research is the study of combined TMS protocols with the consistent use of stimulation of various frequencies, as well as the assessment of the long-term effects of neuromodulation on the development of long-term complications of facial neuropathy, such as pathological synkinesia and contractures.

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